

Evaluation of Land Use/Land Cover Change in Mula-Mutha Watershed, Pune Urban Agglomeration, Maharashtra, India, Based on Remote Sensing Data

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Abstract

Mula-Mutha basin is one of the rapidly urbanizing watersheds, wherein two major urban centers – Pune and Pimpri-Chinchwad have developed at an alarming rate in the last two decades or so. In order to bring out the changes in land use/land cover within this watershed, two images spanning over 19 years were analyzed. This data were supplemented by the field observations and other ancillary data layers which served as the basic sources of data for land cover change detection maps. It was observed that there was a net increase of around 5.33% in the built up area. However this increase is with respect to the entire basin and the actual sprawl is observed near the main urban cores. Most of the development in terms of built up is observed all along the fringe areas of the major settlements and major highways crawling out of the city in all the directions. A significant decrease of 12% was noticed in barren land which is the result of the ever growing city limits and thus the built up areas. Lower values of NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) for the city parts were noticed, which are suggestive of absence of vegetation. However, vegetation cover has increased in the upper and lower reaches of the basin which is attributed to the various watershed management schemes like afforestation, gully bunds, KT weirs, etc. by the local governmental and/or non-governmental organizations especially in the rural areas. It can be concluded that though the level of development has gone up in terms of increasing built up areas it has resulted in the decrease of barren land and the vegetation cover in the watershed.

Keywords: LULC mapping, remote sensing, geographical information systems, Mula-Mutha watershed, Pune

Introduction

Spatial distribution of land use/land cover information and changes in it is desirable for any planning, management and monitoring programmes at local, regional and national levels. This information not only provides a better understanding of land utilization aspects but also plays a vital role in development of any region. The conventional approach of identifying land use land cover changes are costly, low in accuracy and present a picture of only small area (Jaiswal *et al.*, 1999). Remote sensing, because of its capability of synoptic viewing and repetitive coverage, provides useful information on land use/land cover dynamics (Sharma *et al.*, 1989). Depending on the planning context, availability of remote sensing information, and analysis constraints, the extraction of either structural-temporal or functional-temporal land-surface information is most useful. While elaborating on the usage

of remotely sensed data for such studies Prenzel (2004) uses the terms 'land cover' and 'land use' to represent pattern and process or structure and function, respectively. One of the major advantages of remote sensing systems is their capability for repetitive coverage, which is necessary for change detection studies at global and regional scales. Jenson (1986) suggested that detection of changes in the land use/land cover involves use of at least two period data sets. A practical approach to study changes in land use/land cover, which may be caused due to natural/human activities, can be accomplished by using current and archived remotely sensed data (Luong, 1993). With the availability of multi-sensor satellite data at very high spatial, spectral and temporal resolutions, it is now possible to prepare up-to-date and accurate land use/land cover maps in less time, at lower cost and with better accuracy.

The main objective of the present study is to prepare LULC maps for the Mula-Mutha watershed and to assess the changes in various LULC classes using digital remote sensing techniques. The results obtained from such studies will not only reveal the kind of change that occurred but would be of immense help for future planning since the watershed contains rapidly growing urban centers.

Study Area and Methodology

The area under investigation, Mula-Mutha watershed, lies entirely in the Pune district of Maharashtra State and extends from 18° 18' N to 18° 44' N latitude and 73° 20' E to 74° 20' E longitude (Fig.1). The watershed lies on the leeward side of the Sahyadri ranges (Western Ghats) and is a part of the Deccan trap volcanic province. Mula and Mutha rivers which are seasonal in nature originate in Sahyadri ranges and are the tributaries of the mighty Bhima River. Another major stream is River Pawana. Five large dams are constructed on these rivers. The area lies in the rain shadow zone of the Western Ghats and is dominated by semi-arid climate with monsoonal rainfall. The main highlight of the watershed is the location of a major metropolitan city *Pune*, which lies almost at the core of the watershed. *Pimpri-Chinchwad*, two sister cities of Pune have now been transformed into a large industrial hub. The study area has thus witnessed tremendous urban and industrial growth. Estimating and mapping LULC change for this area will prove to be valuable for environmental management and urban planning. To achieve this goal, remote sensing data from two different satellites are been used to map land use changes in the Mula-Mutha river basin during the 19 year period from 1989 to 2008.

Landsat TM 5 data of February 1989 and IRS P6 LISS III data of February 2008 are employed for the present analysis, which were acquired from National Remote Sensing Centre (NRSC), Hyderabad. Table-1 depicts the type of satellite data used for the present study.

Preprocessing of the Data

Both the images were processed for the geometric, atmospheric and radiometric correction in ERDAS 9.1 using standard techniques. Since the spatial resolution of these two images were different (Table-1) they were further resampled and rescaled to 30m resolution.

Table-1: Satellite data used for the study.

Satellite	Sensor	Spatial resolution	Spectral resolution	Acquisition Date
IRS P6	LISS III	23.5m	Bands - 4 Green, Red, IR, SWIR	14 th February 2008
Landsat	TM 5	30m	Bands - 7 Blue, Green, Red, NIR, MIR, TIR, MIR	11 th February 1989

Fig.1: Location map of the study area.

Image Classification

Supervised classification technique with Maximum Likelihood Classifier (MLC) was employed to obtain a LULC classified map for both the images. Training sets were decided on the basis of visual interpretation for 1989 image. Since no landuse maps were available for that period, Survey of India (SOI) topographical maps (47 F/06, 07, 10, 11, 14, 15 and

47J/02, 03, 06 and 07.) on the scale 1:50,000 were used. Extensive field survey was carried out in the months of January and March 2008 to record the GPS readings along with the land use type. These proved to be helpful in refining the training sets for 2008 image and cross-checking the classified images obtained by the supervised classification technique. Five major classes (built up area, agricultural fields, vegetation, water bodies and barren land) were taken in to consideration during the classification process. The classified images were further subjected to accuracy assessment wherein the K-hat (kappa) statistics and overall accuracy was computed.

Derivation of Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

NDVI calculation was done in ERDAS imagine by running the indices option. NDVI uses the combination of band 3 (0.63-0.69 μm) *i.e.* Red band and band 4 (0.76-0.90 μm) *i.e.* Near Infrared band for Landsat TM image. NDVI is representative of plant assimilation condition and its photosynthetic apparatus capacity and biomass concentration (Groten, 1993). NDVI was computed by using the equation-1.

$$\text{NDVI} = \frac{(\text{Near Infra Red} - \text{Red})}{(\text{Near Infra Red} + \text{Red})} = \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{R}}{\text{NIR} + \text{R}} \quad \text{..... eq.1}$$

Results and Discussion

Accuracy Assessment

The accuracy assessment reports are presented in Table-2 & 3. It is clear that the overall accuracy obtained for both the images is above 80% and the kappa statistics is above 0.75, indicating the classification accuracy to be reasonably good to excellent.

Land use/ land cover Change during the Study Period

Main localities, settlements, and reservoirs in the study area are indicated in Fig. 1. Land use map for the year 1989 derived from the supervised classification of the Landsat TM image of 1989 is depicted in Fig. 2. The most important built-up unit is Pune city. It occupies the central position in the watershed at the confluence of Mula and Mutha rivers. Away from the city, except Pimpri-Chinchwad, no significant suburban area can be pointed out. The built up areas which are away from the city comprise mainly of rural settlements.

Vegetation cover is concentrated in the western part of the watershed, which is on the upstream of the Mula-Mutha Basin. Five major reservoirs can also be observed in the western part of the image. Occurrence of barren land can be witnessed in almost every place which is away from the main stream. Agricultural land is found near the streams, mostly in the downstream of Mula-Mutha River. The most significant characteristics of the water bodies of the Mula-Mutha watershed are the five big reservoirs *viz.* Pawana, Mulshi, Varasgaon, Panshet and Khadakvasla. The main rivers of the watershed are Mula, Mutha and Pavana which are east-flowing rivers. Artificial and natural tanks are very small in numbers, mostly found in the eastern part of the watershed.

Table- 2: Error matrix and Accuracy totals February 1989 Reference Data.

Classified Data	Shadow	Built up	Barren land	Agricultural fields	Vegetation	Water bodies	Row Total	Producers Accuracy	Users Accuracy
Shadow	3	0	0	0	1	0	4	33.33%	75.00%
Built up	1	49	7	12	2	0	71	70.00%	69.01%
Barren land	2	14	152	3	9	0	180	91.02%	84.44%
Agricultural fields	0	5	0	31	1	0	37	63.27%	83.78%
Vegetation	2	2	8	3	100	0	115	88.50%	86.96%
Water bodies	1	0	0	0	0	12	13	100%	92.31%
Column Total	9	70	167	49	113	12	420		

Overall Classification Accuracy = 82.62%; Overall Kappa Statistics = 0.7574

Table-3: Error matrix and Accuracy totals February 2008 Reference Data.

Classified Data	Barren land	Built up	Vegetation	Agricultural fields	Water bodies	Row Total	Producers Accuracy	Users Accuracy
Barren land	64	6	9	0	0	79	80.00%	81.01%
Built up	8	37	4	0	0	49	77.08%	75.51%
Vegetation	8	3	83	0	0	94	85.57%	88.30%
Agricultural fields	0	2	1	9	0	12	100%	75%
Water bodies	0	0	0	0	6	6	100%	100%
Column Total	80	48	97	9	6	240		

Overall Classification Accuracy = 82.92%; Overall Kappa Statistics=0.7519

Fig. 3 depicts the land use during February 2008. The built up area has significantly increased near Pune city and its surroundings. Even the cities of Pimpri-Chinchwad have witnessed significant growth. Apart from this, built-up units are also observed on the eastern side of the watershed away from the city. Agricultural settlements on the eastern part of the watershed are slowly transforming into the fringe settlements. Some of the isolated settlements away from the city identified in 1989 are found to be expanding and gradually approaching towards the city. The position of the vegetation cover has remained almost unchanged as compared to 1989 on the western part of the watershed, which is on the upstream of the Mula-Mutha Basin. However, in the downstream regions of the Mula-Mutha catchment the vegetation cover has gone up. This is primarily attributed to the fact that the Government of Maharashtra has initiated several afforestation schemes in the area after 1990. Moreover, the presence of water hyacinth in the rivers has introduced a bias in the task of

identifying the vegetation cover in the downstream. In addition to the five major reservoirs that had been identified in the 1989 image, numerous small man-made bunds have come up during the subsequent period. This is mainly the outcome of various watershed management schemes introduced in the area. The barren land cover has decreased significantly from 1989. Also, the land under cultivation has decreased during this period, especially on the downstream section of the river which may be caused by the change of occupation of many of the residents in the fringe areas. Agricultural activity has remained more or less similar in the upstream areas of the watershed. The amount of barren land in the area has gone down significantly. This may be ascribed to reclamation of more and more lands for residential, industrial and agricultural purposes. It is expected that the percentage of barren land is bound to go down further in the years to come.

Fig.2: Land Use Classified Map, 1989.

Comparison of 1989 and 2008 land use maps reveals that urban growth has occurred mostly in the eastern, southern and south-western directions of the Pune city. The Pimpri-Chinchwad built-up unit has increased its area in the north-western direction. Figure 4 shows the change in built up area during the concerned time period with respect to specific localities. The vegetation near Pune and Pimpri-Chinchwad has reduced drastically, primarily because of increased developmental activities. This includes commercial projects (like IT industries, shopping malls etc.) and huge residential units (like Magarpatta City, Amanora Complex, etc.). In the north of the city, around Ahmednagar Road, a huge industrial complex of Maharashtra Industrial Development Corporation (MIDC) has come up. This has resulted in large space being used for housing projects mainly to occupy working population in the MIDC. From 1989 image, it is evident that this area was earlier barren land.

Fig.3: Land Use Classified Map, 2008.

Change in land use can be noticed in the southern part of Pune city. Katraj area which is having Pune-Bengaluru and Pune-Mumbai highways has also witnessed rapid development near it. The areas around Sinhagad Road have been developing at a rapid pace. In the western part, Kothrud area is developing rapidly. Bavdhan, which was earlier a small village, has now developed into a posh locality. Similar scenario is observed for the Pashan and Sus villages which have developed because of their improved connectivity with the main city. Aundh and Baner, of late, are transforming into one of the most happening places in the city with large-scale residential projects and shopping malls.

The built up area definitely shows a positive change with time. Modern developmental projects have come up for residential and commercial purposes at the expense of agricultural land and vegetation cover. This can be observed clearly near the Hadapsar area where the agricultural land has given way to new construction sites, especially near the Solapur Road. Hinjewadi has developed into a major IT destination in recent years causing the advancement of Pimpri-Chinchwad twin city. The industrial development in Pimpri-Chinchwad has been done at the expense of the barren lands in the vicinity.

Based on the classified images of 1989 and 2008, areas under different land uses were computed in Arc GIS, the results of which are represented in table 4. Built-up area in the watershed has gone up from 13.74% in 1989 to 19.07% in 2008. Thus a net increase of 5.33 % in the built up area was noted during the study period. However, this proportion is in relation with the entire watershed. A closer look at the classified image of 2008 (fig. 3) and the built-up change image (fig. 4) indicates that the actual growth in built-up has occurred near the city. Proportion of barren land has drastically reduced from 42.71% to 33.84% mainly because of conversion into agricultural land and utilization for building projects. The

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area under agriculture and vegetation collectively show an increase of about 3%. This actually reflects increase in agricultural land. Percentage of area under water bodies recorded a meager increase of 0.41%.

Fig.4: Change in built up area at some selected windows in Mula-Mutha Watershed.

Table-4: Area under each land use class as obtained from the supervised classified images.

Land use classes	Feb-1989		Feb-2008		Change	
	km ²	%	km ²	%	km ²	%
Built up	380.44	13.74	527.85	19.07	147.41	5.33
Barren Land	1182.76	42.71	936.92	33.84	-245.84	-8.87
Agriculture + Vegetation	1110.6	40.11	1197.26	43.24	86.66	3.13
Water bodies	95.27	3.44	106.63	3.85	11.36	0.41
	2769.07	100	2768.66	100		

Variations in NDVI (1989-2008)

NDVI is a good indicator of the vegetation cover and its density in an area. The NDVI image of 1989 (Fig. 5a) shows lower values (-0.4 to 0.2) over the city and some fringe areas

near it. In these zones, the presence of buildings, roads and other infra-structural facilities explains the occurrence of lower values of NDVI. The areas near the river banks and the western part of the watershed show higher values (0.3 to 0.5). This is because of relatively dense vegetation in these areas. The NDVI values tend to decrease as one goes towards east. Moderate NDVI values (0.2 to 0.3) can be observed mostly in areas between the Ghats and the city. This can be attributed to the presence of sparse vegetation cover and barren lands with rock exposure. Very high values of NDVI (0.5 to 1) can be noticed in very few places in the ghat section which may indicate the presence of undisturbed thick cover of vegetation. In the water bodies, NDVI values are very low (-1 to -0.4) which is obvious because of absence of vegetation cover.

NDVI values in the 2008 image vary from -0.65 to +0.35. The pattern of NDVI for 2008 (Fig. 5b) again shows lower values (-0.5 to -0.2) for Pune city and Pimpri-Chinchwad with suburban areas. It is evident that the areas with lower values of NDVI have increased considerably in 2008 suggesting decrease in vegetation cover due to expansion of urban areas and industrial growth. In comparison with the city core the areas near the river banks and the western part of the watershed show slightly higher values (-0.1 to 0.1). This is again because of relatively dense vegetation in these areas. When compared with 1989, in 2008 image it can be seen that though the NDVI values have remained almost the same in the upstream areas, however in the downstream, the areas with higher NDVI values have decreased. An appealing fact deciphered from 2008 image is that the Mula channel in the downstream shows very high values of NDVI (0.1 to 0.35). The presence of water hyacinth behind the numerous bunds introduces this bias in the NDVI values. This fact has been verified by on-field survey where it was seen that in the month of February, the rivers in these parts are covered by water hyacinth.

The range of NDVI values is different for 1989 and 2008. The chief cause for this fact is that the vegetation cover has changed its arrangement and orientation with time. So, it is practically impossible to get same ranges of NDVI values for the time period of almost two decades.

Change Detection Analysis using NDVI Values (1989-2008)

It can be inferred from the NDVI images obtained for 1989 and 2008 that there are some clear variations in the amount of area covered by different NDVI value classes. For identifying the areas where the change is observed and the magnitude of the change in either positive or negative direction, change detection analysis was done by using the two NDVI images (Fig. 6).

A striking change in the negative direction can be pointed out by observing the change detection output. The positive change is very less all over the image. The most significant negative change in the NDVI values (-1 to -0.6) is found mostly over the suburban areas of the city. In the downstream locations of the Mula River, in a scattered manner, this maximum negative change can be seen. In close proximity to the Panshet, Mulshi and Pawana dam, such changes are also observed there. This is because a number of tourist resorts, educational institutes and big residential projects have come up in the recent years in these places. A considerable amount of negative change (-0.6 to -0.4) is seen in almost all

over the watershed except the areas near water bodies. Almost no alteration is there in the NDVI values of the water bodies (-0.2 to 0). However, the only positive change in NDVI values (0-1) is observed near the big dams on the western part and in the Mula river near its confluence with the Bhima river. The cause behind the increase in NDVI values near the dams may be the increased agricultural activities in the vicinity as well as plantation activities carried out for beautification purpose. On the eastern part, in Mula River, water hyacinth has developed behind numerous small bunds. Thus, the NDVI values have increased over the time. As water hyacinth is caused by eutrophication, its occurrence may indicate indirectly that the industrial development has affected the natural settings.

Fig. 7a and b depict the relationship between the NDVI values and land use type. In order to represent this relationship, random points were generated which were common for both the images, and then overlaid on the NDVI and land use stacked files to extract the pixel-wise data for both the parameters under consideration. The values obtained showed certain range of NDVI values for each land use class. In order to better represent this variation minimum as well as maximum NDVI values obtained were plotted against the respective land use type. The result (Fig. 7a & 7b) clearly showed that the maximum NDVI values are higher for the 1989 image than the 2008 image. Especially it can be observed that the vegetation class is showing a decreasing trend with time as the maximum value of NDVI is less for 2008. Again from the minimum NDVI value diagram, it can be found that for all the other classes NDVI values are higher for 1989 image except the water bodies. This may be attributed to the fact that the presence of water hyacinth in the Mula River induces a bias in the NDVI values.

Summary and Conclusions

The study undertaken has helped to understand changes in the land use land cover pattern. One of the major factors that identify the changing land use pattern is vegetation, changes in which were studied by comparing Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) maps. The study also highlights the expansion of Pune city over the last two decades, which lies at the center of the watershed. This growth is accompanied with rapid change in the land use pattern where natural landscape is altered and replaced by the cultural landscape.

With the advent of new technologies in constructional (engineering) activities, natural features (like hills, rivers, forests, etc.) do not pose any kind of barrier for developmental work. However, indiscriminate growth in built up structures has led to the changes in the land cover pattern in the Mula Mutha basin. In the last two decades the built up area in this watershed has increased by 5.33% with respect to the total area of the watershed. The main area of concern within the basin is the Pune city and its fringe areas wherein due to rapid urbanization and industrialization the landscape has undergone drastic changes in the study period. Due to haphazard and unplanned growth the Pune city has expanded its arms in Eastern, southern and northwestern direction. These mostly consist of huge township, residential complexes and few IT sectors. Most of the agricultural land from the eastern part of the Pune city (Hadapsar) has been converted to residential one.

(a)

(b)

Fig.5 (a): NDVI Image, 1989 (Landsat TM); b. NDVI Image, 2008 (IRS P6 LISS III).

Fig. 6: Change Detection by Using NDVI Values (1989 & 2008).

In the rural area growth in built up area is relatively less, but it is observed that most of the places associated with large or small waterbodies (like lakes and reservoirs) have sprung up with a number of resorts in the recent past. Even in the upper reaches of the watershed, near the big reservoirs, a number of built up units have been developed which comprise of big residential projects like Lavasa City, personal farmhouses, small agro-based industries, educational institutions etc. With the continuation of these activities, the ecosystem may be hampered which may lead to hazards like landslides. Thus, not only exploitation of the nature but preservation and management of the natural resources with their optimum use is also needed for long-term development.

This kind of development is putting pressure on the environment by introducing pollution of different kinds. Apart from air and water pollution another major problem especially in urban areas of the basin is the occurrences of flash floods during high intensity storm events.

One of the positive impacts of the governmental/non-governmental organizations' watershed schemes is quite visible in terms of increased vegetation cover in the upper and lower reaches of the basin. It appears that afforestation schemes along with other watershed management schemes like contour trenching and small bunds are yielding better results in this basin.

Fig. 7a: NDVI Values Plotted against the Land Use (Upper limit of NDVI); **b.** NDVI Values Plotted against the Land Use (Lower limit of NDVI).

However, the major question is about the future changes in the watershed. Due to presence of Pune and Pimpri-Chinchwad cities, developmental activities associated with urbanization and industrialization will continue in the future too. On one hand though they will lead to economic prosperity of the region, on the other hand they will also create environmental problems such as increasing imperviousness, water pollution, etc. Considering the LULC changes that have occurred and will occur in the future, planners have to initiate the measures that will help in mitigating the environmental hazards those will probably occur. Sustainable development should be encouraged which will give people a chance to use the existing resources wisely over the long term without obstructing the present use of the resources. The city planners should lay down stringent rules for allotment and construction of buildings along the river and on the hill slopes. Certain rules like no construction within 30m of river banks exists but are not implemented. Thus the civic administration should see that proper implementation of such rules is done.

Most importantly huge complexes should be prohibited especially along the first order streams as bunding/obstructing and modifying these streams will have major impact in terms of increased sedimentation, pollutants and discharge.

One of the major finding of the present study indicated the growth in vegetation cover as an effect of watershed management schemes. Thus, it is suggested that more such schemes should be taken up in the upper and middle reaches of the basin and the hills and hill slopes in and around major urban centers should be designated the status of protected hill parks. This will enhance the infiltration capacity and decrease the direct runoff.

Acknowledgements: The authors are grateful to Indian Space Research Organization and University of Pune for providing financial assistance to carry out current research. The authors are also grateful to the anonymous reviewers for providing necessary inputs for the present article.

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